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INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS IN CONTEMPORARY EDUCATION

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Abstract

The main strategy of modern education should focus on the student's independent activity, the organization of self-learning environments and experimental and practical training, where students have a choice of actions and can use initiative as well as flexible training programs where students can work in a comfortable rhythm. Today, we should talk about the use of interactive methods of training, which encourage interest in the profession promote the efficient acquisition of training material form patterns of conduct provide high motivation, strength, knowledge, team spirit and freedom of expression and most importantly, contribute to the complex competences of future specialists. We will give an overview of the modern teaching methods that are most widespread in the scientific and methodological literature and have the potential to form the competences of future professionals. The training, case study, behavioural modelling, peer feedback, play project, metaphor game, storytelling, basket and action learning methods and their potential in professional training are briefly described.

Keywords: Teaching Method; Innovative Method; Professional Competence; Education.

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1. Introduction

Competence-based approach in the system of higher is intended to increase attention to the effective and technological formation of professional competences. Professional competence we understand as a personal education that determines the productivity of professional tasks and includes knowledge, skills and professionally significant personal qualities, experiences and value orientations. In this case, competence differs from such traditional concepts as “knowledge”, “ability”, “skills” and “experience” by its integrative nature, determined by personal traits, such as practice-oriented focus, the ability to work in a wide variety of contexts, self-regulation and self-esteem.

Such a definition of professional competence requires significant changes in the pedagogical support of the university curriculum, filling it with teaching methods which could provide the training of future specialists with the required comprehensive result. The traditional methods of the university educational process are certainly important for professional development. However, their limitations are felt even more acutely at present when a complex phenomenon such as competence is formed. Therefore, we believe that modern education should focus on the student's independent activity, the organization of self-learning environments and experimental and practical training, where students have a choice of actions and can use initiative as well as flexible training programs where students can work in a comfortable rhythm.

Today, we should talk about the use of interactive methods of training, which encourage interest in the profession; promote the efficient acquisition of training materials form patterns of conduct; provide high motivation, strength, knowledge, team spirit and freedom of expression and most importantly, contribute to the complex competences of future specialists.

Hence, we will give an overview of those modern teaching methods which are most widespread in the scientific and methodological literature and have the potential to form the competences of future professionals.

2. Interactive Teaching Methods

2.1. Case Study Method

This method involves ambiguity in the solution of the presented problem, which creates a challenge for discussing the reasoning of proposed solutions and choosing the most appropriate one. Therefore, the result is not only knowledge but also professional skills and a well-formed personality and set of values.

The case which is viewed by the students is usually taken from a real professional area and is supported by visual materials, statistical data, charts and graphs, descriptions of how it is viewed by different people, reports, data from the media, Internet resources, etc.—i.e., the information that allows us to understand what is described in the case. When future teachers are trained a case may be, for instance, a conflict between a teacher and parent based on a student's progress recorded in the class register; the decisions of teacher's councils and boards recorded in the minutes; the student's character as described by classmates, teachers and a school psychologist; and other documents, including school statutes.

Thus, studying and analyzing work experience based on real situations, students comprehensively enrich the knowledge and skills that undergird the professional world, demonstrating a productive effect on the formation of their professional competences.

2.2. Behavioural Modelling

Behaviours that are offered to students using this method should sufficiently comply with actual professional situations, so that future specialists have the opportunity to maximize immersion in professional activities and rapidly adapt to specific conditions.

Behavioural modelling is effective under the following conditions: firstly, the proposed case is attractive to students and arouses their confidence and willingness to follow the proposed model; secondly, the case demonstrates the desired sequence or correct procedure in the standard situation; and thirdly, the students see that compliance with the desired sequence of activities is rewarded.

Thus, the presented method of behavioural modelling can enhance the quality of training by promoting appropriate behaviour in ways typical of future employment situations.

2.3. The Method of Peer Feedback

The method of peer feedback is where one student provides another student ongoing feedback about his/her actions deeds and decisions. A look at their actions and reactions from the outside allows the future specialist to better understand his/her strengths and weaknesses and develop adequate self-esteem. The method of peer feedback is based on information when performing tasks associated with the development of new skills and performing current professional duties. The participants are absolutely equal.

Feedback can be provided after discussions, performances, educational tasks, etc. Practical training, in which students directly solve professional problems, has extraordinary value and opportunities for the implementation of this method. For example, such feedback for future teachers can be given after the lecture or additional training and educational activities, etc.

The students, of course, need to be trained to give objective feedback to make informed judgements and become competent to provide information before using this method.

Thus, the method of peer feedback provides more efficient development of the competences of future professionals through continuous monitoring of activities and opportunities to provide timely assistance and correction of deficiencies.

2.4. Play Projects

Play projects is a teaching method where learning is effected via problem solving. At the first stage the teacher fixes the learning problem, i.e., makes the problem situation a psychological one. At the second stage the students split into two competing groups and craft solutions to the problem. The third stage is a final meeting where students take roles and publicly defend the developed solutions.

Play projects are most successful in practical classes as they involve no explanation of the new material or information exchange between the teacher and the students. Informational, research, creative and applied projects can be done within this format.

Thus, the play project method provides high activity for teaching courses and is more productive because design skills are developed and the specialists will be more flexible and efficient in solving complex professional tasks in the future.

2.5. Metaphor Game

This form of teaching helps activate the creative skills of the students and view a professional situation in a new way, breaking the stereotypes. The metaphor game develops students' creativity, lessens anxiety in problem solving, encourages students' independence, etc. Proverbs, tales, fables and legends which evoke the future professions' problems can serve as metaphors. For example, a game can be based on the idea of the 'Unsmiling Princess' fairy tale when she chooses a husband. Yet the competitors must not make her smile but demonstrate some professional skills.

Therefore, the metaphor game method develops behavioural examples in situations typical of future professional activities; the set metaphoric context focuses the students on creatively solving professional problems, which is productive for the development of all components of professional competence.

2.6. Storytelling

Storytelling teaches future professionals the rules of work with the help of myths and stories from professional life. Speaking about the content of professional work, its specificity and emerging situations, the teacher prepares the student for understanding traditions, philosophy, culture and professional activities. Maximum objective information should be provided to avoid the future specialist's disappointment in his/her occupational choice. The method helps the students quickly learn the specifics of the job, governing documents, career prospects, etc.

This method helps students adapt more quickly to the profession and form value judgements of the professional activities as a whole and their role in society, which is fundamental for the professional competency of the future specialist.

2.7. Basket-Method

The basket-method is a method of learning based on imitation of the most common situation of specialists, when the student has to perform unplanned activities efficiently. The contents of this method are as follows: student is presented the situation or the role he/she should play and the materials which he/she must use in the exercise; the student performs the proposed actions; the final interview is conducted, in which the student justifies his/her actions, describes the potential impact of an action and assesses personal satisfaction with the result. The teacher analyses the information received from the students, offers an alternative solution, highlights missed opportunities, predicts the results of decisions and makes recommendations for the future.

This method, unlike the others, requires the development of scenarios and role-playing. This method can not only create a practical mode of professional competence. It can also develop the stress resistance of the future professional while playing out possible interventions in the process of solving the present problem.

2.8. The Method of Action Learning

The method of action learning has recently become one of the promising areas of modern education, as it provides the organization of self-learning environments. This teaching method allows students to effectively solve problems of practice-focused training.

This method is implemented in group work among students. During the joint work on the problem students develop their own way to a comprehensive solution, justify that solution and conduct a presentation of their proposals. A group of teachers discusses the results of the public defence and names the winner, which makes evaluation more objective.

If this method is used by students during the period of work experience, the problems to be solved may be taken from a particular practice, which enhances the teaching potential of the method and the results obtained in the course of its implementation. Thus, learning by doing has a positive influence on the components of professional competence through practical skills which develop the organization of joint activities and taking responsibility for one's work.

3. Conclusion

To conclude the review, we note that active learning methods modify the role of the teacher from the translator of information to the organizer and coordinator of the educational process and make it possible to form complex competences in future professional specialties via student activities that manifest as closely as possible the content of professional work.

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